

IRONY AS A LINGUISTICAL CATEGORY

Zayniddinov Ma'rufjon Farxodovich

Aydinov Tursunmurod Yusipovich

Teachers of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069836>

Expression image tools in the system sarcasm to himself special there is a place. Already this image method expression purpose and effect to the power according to another image tools with certain level integrity and different aspects in itself incarnate is enough Irony about thought wins we are this about said many views, opinions note reached transition is appropriate.

Irony about thought S.I. _ Pokhodnya , his the author or speaker by in advance planned, thinking put , speech formed like signs is available no matter what is enough Therefore _ too sarcasm of the subject common situation manages and his each one separately moment for too importance occupation reaches [1, 22].

of G. V. Kolshansky conclusions according to irony sentence of the text in the communicative plan thinking with depends aspects of it communicative demand , command and another characters sure expression to deliver service does _ [2, 22].

Author's sarcastic the idea in expression own intention , ie sarcastic the sentence in making thoughts reflection presentation , speech content and in it incarnate has been in the facility linguistically standard , i.e the goal done increase for formed text sarcasm expression is an object .

Note reach maybe sarcastic _ of the text in formation language of units speech activity in getting dictionary of units sure contextual expensive have to be note will be done .

This about VV Vinogradov in his views speech of devices artistic in works structural structure and his substantive content of the author point of view view and to the relationship relying on justified note will be done . [4, 85].

X. of Weinrich in his views sarcastic expression for linguistically essence expression plan with contextual and situational in aspect organic to be it is necessary

Sarcastic thought in formation contextual of essence this text of components connotative and associative to relations too depend _ Include in formation of G. V. Kolshansky views based on so to speak , every how sentence certain movement and of the situation from the expression consists of The sentence is undoubtedly one communication act within is formed . This is it situation speech purpose and instead of come came out without to himself special reality with depends feature represents [2, 29].

Sarcastic of your opinion formation sentence communicative directed with too depends . Because such thought of our notice too to himself special there are grounds , of course . In this sentence structure own of components which in place , how to the location , that is propositional formation depends . This is it condition express sarcastic in being and his how thought in delivery place to himself feature with is connected . Irony of expression basics language of the structure differently levels of units activation with depend _ This point of view

from the point of view when viewed , this the goal incarnate Note the context done features to express able to be necessary [3].

Of course , sarcasm about thought announcements that 's it expression image of the tool in expression complicated and high cultural expression responsibility existence separately note to reach appropriate that we count . In this to himself special and sometimes unique sarcastic of expressions formation and communicative act perspective in terms of high degree philosophical , aesthetic, communicative task perform place with laughter and mental effect provoke separately are features . Therefore _ too this expression tool in the composition propositional and presuppositional aspects incarnate is counted . So sarcasm _ _ as a specific concept not him _ wide as a branch category learning matter essence wide and sure imagination reach enable gives _

Saying OK , it's fine or partially laughter instigator of this category of people mutually communicative in their relationship intended and expected to the results reach from the roads one requirement is enough That's why for too of society different in networks his of possibilities appropriate and purposeful use social importance occupation is enough Sometimes his place in communication different approach do it to get able not to be too can _ This is the feature with this category itself special social to the character have and aesthetic status with another expression image of means different stands.

References:

- 1.Pokhodnya S.I. Yazykovye vidy i sredstva realizatsii ironii// Pokhodnya S.I. - Kyiv: Naukovaya dumka, 1989. -128 p.
- 2.Kolshansky G.V. Context semantics // Kolshansky G.V. - Moscow: Nauka, 1980.
- 3.Serdyuk A. Sposoby vyrajaniya humor, ironii i satiry i model ix perevoda na zanyatiyax po bulgarskoy literature // Plovdiv University " Paisiy xilendarski " – Bulgarian nauchni Trudove , roof 49, kn. 1, sb. g, 2011 - philology, paisiy Hilendarsky university of Plovdiv - Bulgaria research papers , vol . 49, book 1, part d , 2011 – languages oath literature
- 4.https://studbooks.net/586299/literatura/yazykovye_sredstva_vyrazheniya_ironii_hudozhestvennom_proizvedenii